

Increasing Profit with Amazon Advertising

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ABSTRACT

The most common form of amazon Price Per Click (PPC) campaign optimization comes through weeks of trial and error, testing and analysis. Many experts in the field of PPC advertising will spend weeks gathering data. They spend large amounts of money in filtering, analyzing, and consolidating data only to narrow it down and repeat the process. This process can go through multiple iterations and in some cases becomes an indefinite process of trial and error. In his article entitled "The Most Comprehensive Guide to Optimizing Your Amazon Sponsored Ads (PPC Campaign)." Taylor Benterud⁴ said, "I advise you make tiny changes.. Maybe 13 words and then test the effects over a 10-15 day period and repeat... I advise testing different types of bids for each match type every 7 days." This process has been tested and works, but it is very financially costly, especially testing for months to find out what works. In a paper that Kiri Masters⁵ authored she said, "a fully-realized PPC campaign is something that must be cultivated, like a garden." These methods take too much time and are subject to human error and changes in amazon structure over time. Buying Media⁶ research shows that Amazon Ad revenue has gone up by no less than 25.3% over last six years with a max increase from 2011 to 2012 of 64.2%. This clearly shows that there are more and more people joining in the Amazon advertising game which means that it is a crucial aspect of selling on Amazon that must be mastered if a seller wants to stay competitive in this market. This paper will describe our approach to maximize the profit of an Amazon.com advertising campaign for a the product *Exactly Write*, a writing utensil aid. We took the principles that are explained in the "Drive Sales with Amazon Marketing Services."⁸ article to make the objective function in an effort to maximize profit by maximizing net revenue and minimizing cost. The model used for cost is accurate and complete; however, the model used to calculate only an estimation based on the data that we collected, and only approximates revenue. The approximation is close to real data, and is sufficient for this project especially around the region that we wish to optimize in.

1 Introduction

Amazon.com is built on search algorithms similar to Google or Facebook that determines which results to display based on the key words the user inputs. Search algorithms are only successful in as much as they provide the user information that he/she is looking for. In order to determine what to display, the search algorithm takes into account many factors. Amazon's search algorithm takes into account average review score for a particular product, the number of reviews for that product, the number of sales that the item has, etc. This causes newer products to be at a disadvantage since they have few reviews and few sales in comparison to competing products that have been on amazon for a while. In order to combat this disadvantage, sellers can purchase advertising that causes the product to appear when the customer is searching for a product similar to the seller's product by associating it through keywords. As customers notice the advertised item and purchase it, the higher the product will appear on the queue. If a product can get up to the top of page one, it will obtain stability and likely stay at the top for the life of the product. As complicated and intricate as the Amazon algorithms are, amazon.com gives sellers give very little information on improving their advertisement campaign⁷.

Sellers purchase advertisement by bidding on keywords that associate the product with it. Amazon.com sells keywords by bidding, i.e. the seller places a bid on a keyword. The higher the bid, the more the product will

be advertised, and if a customer clicks on the product while searching with this specific keyword, the seller is charged a fee. Amazon.com performs its own optimization for bid price for a given keyword and informs the seller, and thus we are not concerned with optimizing the bid price for a specific keyword, but we are interested in determining which keywords to use and which ones to remove since some are more costly than others and can cause the owner to lose money. The key words used can be adjusted by changing the bid. As the bid decreases, costly keywords are removed. This has a great impact on the sales of the product simply because in general, the key words that are searched with higher frequency will be more expensive in terms of how much the seller must pay in order to compete for advertisement space in that keyword. It is crucial for sellers to get high traffic to their products as this results in more sales and in return, a reward from the amazon algorithm for increasing rank. As a product increases rank it will receive more and more traffic which in turn results in better ranking. The rank does not have a linear relationship with sales rather an exponential. This is a prime case of the saying, "The rich get richer." Since this is the case, amazon sellers must win the advertising game if they wish to have success with their products. The results of this study will greatly increase the chances that a seller will know exactly where to bid their advertisements to get maximum return. It is important to realize that a seller could bid too high for their category and end up unnecessarily wasting large amounts of money if the bid is placed too high. It is important to find the sweet spot in order to maximize return of investment (ROI).

Having a product displayed does not guarantee a sale; the product needs to be appealing. The product can be more appealing by adjusting price and making the merchandise a prime merchandise or not. Currently there are more prime members on amazon than non-prime members, and about seventy percent of the sales are prime merchandise; however, to make a product a prime merchandise, the seller has to cover the shipping cost instead of the buyer. This is a another factor to consider. In summary, this project aims at maximizing the profit of an Amazon advertising campaign by adjusting the price, advertising bid, and whether the product is prime merchandise or not.

We understand that there are other factors that go into the success of a advertising campaign such as headline of the product.[9] We are not including these factors in our analysis as they are difficult to quantify. In the case of a headline it is near to impossible to test all combinations of words that make up a title and this aspect of Amazon selling is outside the scope of our project.

2 Description

The purpose of the objective function is to maximize profit over a two month span by adjusting the product cost (P_c), advertising bid (bid), and whether the product is prime merchandise or not ($Prime$). Table 1 shows a list of the variables used, a description of each, their value, and lower and upper bounds for the design variables.

The design variables P_c and bid are treated as continuous and $Prime$ is discrete.

Due to the complexity of the objective function, it will be broken down into smaller parts to gain an understanding of its entirety.

$$\text{maximize } profit \tag{1a}$$

$$s.t. \quad 0 \leq P_c \leq 13 \tag{1b}$$

$$0.1 \leq bid \leq 0.3 \tag{1c}$$

$$profit = revenue - cost \tag{2a}$$

$$revenue = numSold * P_c \tag{2b}$$

Variable Name	Description	Value
<i>Pc</i>	Product Cost	[10,15]
<i>bid</i>	Advertising Bid	[0.1,0.3]
<i>Prime</i>	Prime merchandise or not	[0,1]
<i>Cc</i>	Competitor's product cost	\$11.99
<i>COM</i>	Cost of Manufacturing 1 item	\$2.30
<i>COS</i>	Cost of Shipping 1 item	\$2.56
<i>amazonCut</i>	Percent of <i>PC</i> Amazon keeps	0.15
<i>clicks</i>	Average number of clicks	$f(bid)$
<i>conversionRate</i>	Purchases per <i>clicks</i>	0.0468
<i>avgCPC</i>	Average Cost Per Click	$f(bid)$
<i>percentRetained</i>	Percent of non-Prime customers	$f(Prime)$

- Indicates that it is a design variable

Table 1. Variables

$$cost = advCost + (COM + COS * prime + Pc * amazonCut) * numSold \quad (2c)$$

$$numSold = conversionRate * adjClicks * percentRetained \quad (2d)$$

$$adjClicks = (-atan(4 * (Pc + COS * !prime - Cc)) / pi * clicks * 2 + clicks) \quad (2e)$$

$$advCost = avgCPC * adjClicks \quad (2f)$$

where *percentRetained* is a function of *prime*, and *clicks* and *advCPC* are a function of bid generated using the best fit method on data that shows the relationship between *bid* and the two variable.

The function for *adjClicks* estimates the effect that changing the price would have on the number of clicks the item would have. Notice that the cost of shipping is added to the product cost when the merchandise is not prime. This is to take into account the the shipping cost that customers will have to pay for shipping instead of the seller. This function is the only function we modeled based on intuition since it would be very costly to adjust it and collect data on it.

3 Preliminary Results

Since the design variable *prime* is discrete and only takes on two values [0, 1], it was most efficient to manually adjust this variable and run the optimization twice, once fore each value *prime* can assume. We initially ran the optimization without any lower or upper bounds, and the results were unrealistic due to the functions that modeled average cost per click and number of clicks as a function of *bid*. These functions are shown in figure 1.

Fig. 1. The figure shows the functions average cost per click and number of clicks as a function of bid.

According to the figure 1, $avgCPC$ becomes negative as bid tends to zero. Also, the numbers of clicks drops significantly as bid becomes greater than 0.31. These errors in our models are from the lack of data to expand the entire domain of bid . In order to compensate for this error, upper and lower bounds were added to the design variables as shown in table 1. This forces the objective function to work in the region that we have reliable data. If the solution to the optimization was at a lower or upper bound of the reliable portion of the model, than we would have to collect more data to expand the model; however, this was not the case. Thus, our model of our function is reliable within the region of interest.

With the upper and lower bounds constraining the optimization function to remain in a reliable region, the objective function was optimized twice: once for *prime* and once for not *prime*. The results are shown in table 2.

The product cost of the merchandise needed to be higher for prime merchandise than for non prime merchandise. This is to account for the burden of shipping cost moving from the seller to the buyer. If the cost of shipping was added to the non-Prime product cost, the total would be \$ 11.78 which is almost the same as the optimized product cost for prime merchandise, but this is not the cause in the difference of profit.

The difference in profit is due to the amount of customers lost or products sold when it is not a prime merchandise(this difference in number sold is shown in table 2). The average Amazon Prime consumer spends more than 200% more than a non Amazon Prime consumer, and a little more than half of the consumers are Amazon Prime members.³ This suggests that two thirds of the sales would be lost by making the merchandise non-prime. This is supported by our calculations, $40/3 \approx 13$.

In order to maximize the profit, the product cost is slightly below the competitor's cost which is \$11.99. This

	Profit	Product Cost	Bid	Number Sold
Prime	\$ 41.09	\$ 11.73	\$ 0.22	40
Not Prime	\$ 10.33	\$ 9.22	\$ 0.20	13

Table 2. Optimized Function

would give the seller a slight advantage until the competitors lower the price of their merchandise to equal the lowest price. Table 3 shows the profit and the number of products sold in a 2 month period if the price was left the same. By decreasing the price, number of sales would increase by 12 and profit would increase to \$40, but once the competitors lower their price, the number of sales would decrease to 28 and the profit would decrease to \$27. This indicates that after lowering the price, the seller would be worse off after 6 months.

	Profit	Product Cost	Bid	Number Sold
Prime	\$ 33	\$ 11.99	\$ 0.22	28
Not Prime	\$ 2	\$ 9.43	\$ 0.20	1

Table 3. Optimized Function With Product Cost Constant

The last thing that the seller can do is to adjust the bid price. Adjusting the bid price determines which key words the seller uses since some key words are more expensive than others. Originally the product was being advertised with a max bid of \$ 0.30, but the optimizer suggests lowering it to \$0.22. This indicates that the seller will lose money with pricier keywords.

4 Conclusion

Optimally utilizing Amazon Sponsored Products will enable a seller to outsell competing products in a specific niche.¹⁰ The results shows that the objective function is most sensitive to *prime*, and by making a product a prime merchandise is the best thing to increase profit. The next best thing to maximize profit is to lower the max bid to remove the keywords that are causing the seller to lose money. The last option is to lower the product cost. By lowering the product cost by \$0.26, the number of products sold increased by %150 and profit increased by \$ 8.00; however, in the long run after the competitors adjust their price, the number sold would resume its previous value, and profit would decrease from the original profit by %5. thus, in order to maximize profit in the long run, the product should be prime merchandise, the bid for advertisement should be \$0.22 per click, and the price should not change.

5 References

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